

PUPILS PERSONAL PROFILE AND PARENTING STYLES: INPUT TO LEARNERS' RESPONSIVE BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

Education is one of the relevant industries caught in the middle of this pandemic, and the Philippines has millions of affected learners all over the country. Incidentally, it is necessary to safeguard the education sector through strategies that guarantee the continuous flow of learning to integrate online with offline approaches. The researcher aimed to present the difficulties and experiences faced by the learners on Modular Distance Learning. A descriptive, qualitative research was conducted and used an online survey, interview, and observation as tools to gather data and to find out the problems encountered by the learners on this mode of learning. Moore's theory on Transactional Distance Learning served as the framework of analysis and the researcher analyzed the results by thematic coding. A total of 45 learners participated in the online survey and 10 learners participated in online interview. Questions in the survey elicit the situations of the learners and how they managed to study on their own in the absence of learning facilitators to guide them. The result of the survey conducted to section HUMMS 11- Kohlberg determine the accessibility and availability of the gadgets that will be used for modular distance learning, it was revealed that most of the learners' used cellphones to access FB messenger, group chat and google meet for online classes. Learners engaged themselves in understanding the concepts presented in the module as they developed a sense of responsibility in learning on their own and in accomplishing the tasks provided in the module, with limited assistance from the teacher, these learners progress on their own. Today, as the country is at the state of emergency health crisis, these SLMs for Modular Distance Learning were the most convenient, and appropriate to use for our learners to continue learning amidst of Covid -19 pandemic.

Keywords: mode of learning, transactional distance learning, modular distance learning, online survey, online interview